

CLINICAL INDICATORS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT OF ORAL LEUKOPLAKIA

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The study included 40 patients (20 men and 20 women) aged 35 to 65 years with a clinically and histologically confirmed diagnosis of leukoplakia. Inclusion criteria: the presence of leukoplakia foci on the mucous membrane of the cheeks, tongue, and floor of the oral cavity. Patients after surgical treatment of leukoplakia of the oral mucosa were prescribed KIN Care gel for topical use 2 times a day after oral sanitation for 8 days.

As complaints, pain in the oral mucosa was recorded as the most frequent symptom, noted in 92% of patients, in addition, many associated the feeling of pain with a burning sensation in the oral cavity, noted in 37% of cases. In addition, roughness of the oral mucosa, a feeling of tightness of the mucosa and a feeling of dryness of the oral mucosa were noted. 18% noted a feeling of awkwardness or an unpleasant sensation during functional actions of the oral cavity. In 9% of patients, there were no complaints.

The performed analysis of anamnestic data from questionnaires filled in by patients allowed us to identify possible risk factors for the development of precancerous diseases. These include, first of all, tobacco smoking, which implies not only smoking cigarettes, including electronic ones, but also the use of NAS, which is typical for our region - 72.32% of cases. In second place, at 21.7%, is alcoholism, or regular consumption of alcoholic beverages. In addition, background pathology was noted, i.e. somatic diseases that weaken the body's immune system - in 23.7%. Among them, it is worth noting gastrointestinal pathology in 45% and

cardiovascular diseases in 32%. Nervous system lesions in the form of depression and chronic fatigue with stress were recorded in 28%.

All patients studied underwent surgical excision of the lesion (laser, cryodestruction, scalpel), after which conservative therapy of the wound surface was prescribed using keratoplasty.

By the 4th day of treatment, subjective complaints (burning, dryness, discomfort when eating) significantly decreased in 34 patients (85%, $p < 0.01$). Complete Epithelialization of the affected area was observed in 31 patients (77.5%) by the 8th day of treatment, partial - in 6 patients (15%), no positive dynamics - in 3 patients (7.5%).

The objective reduction in the lesion area (based on clinical photographs and a calibrated ruler) averaged 62% by day 4 and 89% by day 8 ($p < 0.001$). The level of improvement (more than 50% reduction in lesion area) was achieved in 35 patients (87.5%).